

MILEATONE 1

C-mapER

MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS

CmapER project

Case studies thematic maps

MILISTONE 1

JULY 2018

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Sibilla M, Kurl E, (2018), Ten data sheets and thematic maps, H2020 MCSA IF 2016, Technical Report, Milestone 1

Available online: www.energyretrofitlearningplatform.org

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TEN DATA SHEETS AND THEMATIC MAPS

Introduction

This report fulfils the requirements of Milestone 1 (M 1). It follows Deliverable 1.1 and 1.2 (D.1.1. and D. 1.2) , which previously reported on the state-of the-art on the transdisciplinary approach to Energy Retrofit and the analysis of 10 case studies.

The aim of this report is to transfer information from text to map form. Here, the case studies are presented in form of data sheets in order to enhance the comparison focussing for each case study on one piece of information.

The structure of data sheet is very simple. A first set of information concerns general data (i.e. name, place, data and original and current function). A list of keywords anticipated the concept that will be proposed in form of map. The second and third section of the data sheet introduces respectively the “Climatic Features” and the “Bioclimatic Features”

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MILESTONE 1.1

1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: URBAN RETROFIT

CONTEXT: CITY OF SALZBURG, AUSTRIA

ORIGINAL USE: MIX

USE: MIX

DESIGNER(S): ND

COMPLETION DATE: 2013

KEY WORDS: District Heating, Integrate Renewable Energy in existing building, Solar Collector, Micro-net, Social Aspects of Energy Retrofit, Decision-making processes, Tenants Behaviour, Urban quality, Reduction of the heat demand.

2. CLIMATIC FEATURES

CLIMATE SUMMARY:

- MONTHLY DATA: RADIATION (W/mq); MAX, MID, MIN TEMPERATURE °C
- PREVALLING WIND (WIND FREQUENCY – Hrs)
- HOURLY DATA – MONTHLY DIURNAL AVERAGES
- DAILY CONDITION (1ST JAN

3.BIOCLIMATIC FEATURES

- OPTIMUM ORIENTATION
- COMBINATION OF PASSIVE ENERGY STRATEGIES

4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The challenge to integrate renewable energy in existing supply system was solved by following a strategy based on solar energy and district heating system. But there are additional improvements necessary to meet the goal of high share of renewable energy. Increase solar fraction is achieved by installation of a heat pump in order to increase efficiency of solar collector fields. In addition to that also an own micro-net for heat supply is foreseen. This micro-net in combination with planning directives for all of the housing projects allows low temperatures and thus also higher solar gains.

Heat supply concept with solar collector fields, storage tank and micro-net

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

What strategies to innovate energy infrastructure and buildings?

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6. REFERENCES

Helmut Strasser, Boris Mahler, Norbert Dorfinger, Solar energy in urban community in City of Salzburg, Austria, Word Renewable Energy congress, 2011, Sweden 8-13 May 2011

Helmut Strasser, IEA Annex 51 – Guidelines and Case Studies for Energy Efficient Communities Subtask B: Case Studies on Energy Planning and Implementation Strategy for Neighbourhoods, Quarters and Municipal Areas" Case Study for Austria: stadtwerk:lehen, Salzburg, 2010

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: SOCIAL HOUSING LA CITÉ DU CENTENAIRE

CONTEXT: CHARLEROI, BELGIUM

ORIGINAL USE: SOCIAL HOUSING

USE: SOCIAL HOUSING

DESIGNER(S): STRARTECH MANAGEMENT GROUP

COMPLETION DATE: 2017

KEY WORDS:Reduction the Environmental Footprint, Balanced Choice of Materials, Comfort of the Inhabitants, Environmental Performance, Aesthetic Values, Active participation, Artistic expression

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2. CLIMATIC FEATURES

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The main concern of this intervention is to create a pleasant and generous living environment for the occupants in a neighbourhood on a human scale. The objectives are: - To give a residential character and to personalize the buildings by asserting each building as a different entity in order to break their repetitive and depreciative character; - To adopt a sobriety in the architectural and artistic expression by the employment of a clear vocabulary aimed at efficiency by a balanced choice of materials, selected above all for their environmental performance and their effect on the aesthetics of the premises; - Improve the comfort of the inhabitants by increasing the living area of the dwellings; - Propose a range of housing units that allow a wide range of housing; - Limit the energy costs of the tenants by favouring the passive design for the renovation of the houses; - Reduce the environmental footprint; - To favour the modes of soft travel by reducing the pressure generated by the presence of the automobile. The project is therefore not limited to a simple renovation of housing but to a global overhaul and a complete requalification of the neighbourhood.

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6. REFERENCES

Case Study : Rehabilitation of the Cité du Centenaire in Montignies-surSambre in an eco-district
Website : <https://www.construction21.org/>

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: HALLE PAJOL REFURBISHMENT

CONTEXT: PARIS, FRANCE

ORIGINAL USE: RAILWAY STORAGE

USE: MIX USE

DESIGNER(S): JAP JOURDA ARCHITECTES PARIS

CONSTRUCTION PERIOD: 2011-2013

Keywords: Functional Programme, Diversified functional mix, Ecological aspect, Recyclable material, Production from renewable sources, the relation between architecture and citizens, Need and requirements of the local population,

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The requalification of the old Halle Pajol railway warehouses, located near the Gare de l'Est in the 18th arrondissement, in the hear of the La Chappelle district in Paris, is a unique and ambitious project through which the JAP practice – Jurda Architect Paris – has managed to enhance not only an old building but the entire district at the same time giving it a new vitality and a perspective or cultural and social re-birth. It is infact through the re-functionalization and the refurbishment of a steel building belonging to the 19th century industrial heritage that the French architect Françoise Helen Jourda manage to renew and completely transform the area enhancing the ecological aspect and the relation between architecture and citizens, with the objective to improve the quality of life and promote the awareness of an eco-sustainable architecture.

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

How to enhance the relation between architecture and citizens?

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6. REFERENCES

Jourda, F.H. (11-12-2013) Réhabilitation de la Halle Pajoleet creation d'unejardin public, Paris 18e. Le courrier de l'architecte.Bezocht 21-10-2015 via:

http://www.lecourrierdelarchitecte.com/article_5101

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: SECONDARY SCHOOL SOLITUDE-GYMNASIUM

CONTEXT: STUTTGARD, GERMANY

ORIGINAL USE: SCHOOL 1970

USE: SCHOOL

DESIGNER(S): ND

COMPLETION DATE: 2014

KEYWORDS: Monitoring technology, Communication technology, the Reduction of Energy Consumption, Building envelope, Ventilation systems, Indoor environmental quality, Indoor air quality

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2. CLIMATIC FEATURES

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The Solitude-Gymnasium is a secondary school located in the north-western outskirts of Stuttgart. The entire school had to be renovated because of structural damages at the buildings. Since the energy consumption of the building was very high in comparison to other schools of Stuttgart an energy retrofit was planned. By means of the financial support of the European Commission within the project “School of the Future – Towards zero emission with high performance indoor environment” the total school will be improved in order to decline the energy consumption crucially. The objective of the project for the demonstration partner City of Stuttgart is to reduce the total energy consumption of the Solitude-Gymnasium by the factor 3 and the heat consumption by 75 %. Besides the indoor environmental quality within the class rooms will be improved.

Building	Component	U-value [W/m²K]	Technology
Big pavilion	Walls	0.23	ETICS/curtain wall facade (14 cm of PS/MW)
	Main roof	0.19	16 cm of expanded polystyrene (EPS)
	Middle roof	0.20	14 cm of EPS
	Windows north	0.90	Triple-glazed
	Windows south	1.30	Double-glazed
	Glazed façade hallway	1.20	Double-glazed
Building of scientific classes	Walls	0.18	ETICS/curtain wall facade (18 cm of PS)
	Roof	0.15	22 cm of EPS
	Dome lights	1.10	
	Windows	0.90	Triple-glazed
Main building	Glazed façade	0.70 glazing 1.20 frames 0.30 panels	Triple-glazed
	Walls	0.18	ETICS/curtain wall facade (18 cm of PS)
	Roof	0.17	19 cm of EPS
Gym	Windows	0.90	Triple-glazed
	Walls	0.18	18 cm of mineral wool (MW)
	Roof	0.20	17.5 cm EPS
	Windows	0.90	Triple-glazed

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

How to manage energy consumption?

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6. REFERENCES

Stephan Kempe, Christoph Höfle, Jürgen Görres, Heike Erhorn-Kluttig, Hans Erhorn, Heinz-Michael Beckert, School of the Future: Deep renovation of the Solitude-Gymnasium in Stuttgart, Energy Procedia 78 (2015) 3312 – 3317

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: RENOVATION OF A FORMER INDUSTRIAL SITE

CONTEXT: PISTOIA, IT

ORIGINAL USE: INDUSTRIAL SITE

USE: LIBRARY

DESIGNER(S): PICA CIAMARRA ASSOCIATE

COMPLETION DATE: 2007

Keywords: Architectural Expression, Modest Transformations, Natural Lighting, Sun Chimneys, Natural ventilation systems, Natural difference pressure, Air extraction, Development and progress of this city, City's cultural life

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2. CLIMATIC FEATURES

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The intervention in the former Breda area - area east of Pistoia - new headquarters of the San Giorgio Library, is an intervention that lives by precise spatial limits. The project tends to capture the need for image of public works, that is, it does not interpret the existing to recover it, but to materialize the political vision, in the etymological sense of the term, which is underlying the decision to implement an intervention in that context significant of the city's cultural life. In this framework, the basic question of this intervention was how, in that context, to activate only modest transformations. The basic question was not just to satisfy the "library" function, but to weave in the new architectural expression the memory of the factory e the sense of a research tool inherent in a library. A library that is not "deposit", but a tool for multimedia interactions to link memory and the future. From an architectural point of view, the design themes tend to relate built / not built; dematerialize the built volume; determine a diversified internal spatiality ; solve the question of the thickness of the buildings introducing light capture and natural ventilation systems of interior spaces.

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

How to integrate bioclimatic strategies?

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6. REFERENCES

<http://www.sangiorgio.comune.pistoia.it/assets/files/download/Documentazione-progetto-nuova-biblioteca/progettoarchitettonico.pdf>

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: MALTA STOCK EXCHANGE

CONTEXT: VALLETTA, MALTA

ORIGINAL USE: BRITISH GARRISON CHAPEL (1855)

USE: OFFICE

DESIGNER(S): BRITISH ROYAL ENGINEERS (Original project)

COMPLETION DATE: 2001

KEYWORDS: Active system, Passive systems, Building Management System (BMS), Bioclimatic strategies, Passive draught evaporative cooling system (PDEC), Night time convective ventilation (passive night cooling), Well-being, Adaptability of Protected Building.

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The project proposes a hybrid draught cooling system in order to maintain the comfortable indoor conditions in the central atrium of the Malta Stock Exchange. So, while the cellular offices surrounding the atrium and meeting rooms are air-conditioned, the 14 meter high atrium avoids the need for conventional air conditioning which reduces energy and maintenance costs. During the summer, the air in the atrium is cooled either by evaporative cooling by means of hydraulic nozzles or by indirect cooling by chilled water coils.

5. FOCUS QUESTIONA AND MAP

How to increase the efficiency and ecology of building plant systems?

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6. REFERENCES

<http://www.ehcmmap.eu/intellectual-outputs>

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: BRANDENGEN SCHOOL

CONTEXT: DRAMMEN, NORWAY

ORIGINAL USE: SCHOOL 1914

USE: MULTI-FAMILY HOUSING

DESIGNER(S): ARNSTEIN ARNEBERG (ORIGINAL)

COMPLETION DATE: 2003

Keywords: Internal insulation, Moisture, Space heating control, Ventilation control, Lighting control, Building energy management system (BEMS), Buildings' aesthetics, Affordable operational and maintenance costs

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2. CLIMATIC FEATURES

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The windows have been replaced at different times since 1965. As the windows have caused high heating costs and haven't contributed to an optimal indoor climate, the municipality decided to replace all windows installed after 1965, aiming for new high performance windows, which also pay respect to the historic aspects of the buildings' aesthetics. Existing original windows are being refurbished. Most of the original windows are located along corridors, where the indoor temperature requirements are not as strict as in classrooms. Design criteria for new windows were elaborated in co-operation between the architect N. Herland, a+form, the window manufacturer NorDan, and S. Tangen from the School of the Future Advisory and Evaluation Group. Searching for modern high performance windows the following criteria were required: Looking similar to the original windows from 1914, Long life expectation, $U\text{-value} \leq 0.8 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (at affordable price), Affordable operational and maintenance costs.

Façade detail showing new passive house windows from NorDan (left); close up photo of new window (middle) - Photos: S. Røgeberg. Mai 2012; vertical section with the insulated frames (right).

Glazing specifications	U-value [W/m ² K]	Light transmission [%]	g-value [%]
Ground floor with exterior security glazing: Lam m/energi 2s VKS/Ar 6,38ES+16G+4+16G+ES6	0,53	56	35
Solar glazing on south and west façades: SKN165 m/Energi VKS/Ar 6"-14G+4+16G+ES4	0,58	48	27
Other windows have standard glazing: Energi 2s VKS/Ar 4ES+16G+4+16G+ES4	0,53	58	37

Characteristics of the windows of Brandengen School after the retrofit.

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

How to improve the performance of the building envelope?

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6. REFERENCES

HeikeErhorn-KluttigHansErhorn, School of the Future – Towards Zero Emission with High Performance Indoor Environment, Energy Procedia, Volume 48, 2014, Pages 1468-1473

M. Zinziet al, School of the Future Towards Zero Emission with High Performance Indoor Environment, Report Deliverable D6.1Design Phase Report, 2013,
<https://www.school-of-the-future.eu/>

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: RESIDENTIAL NEIGHBOURHOOD JUAN XXIII

CONTEXT: ALICANTE, SPAIN

ORIGINAL USE: HOUSING 1967

USE: HOUSING

DESIGNER(S): ND

COMPLETION DATE: 2011

KEYWORDS: Economically Feasible Projects, Real Estate Market, Job Creation, Representative groups, Energy services companies, Low-income families, Energy services companies, Profile of energy poverty, Risk of Exclusion, Geographic Concentration of Obsolete Buildings

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2. CLIMATIC FEATURES

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

The main goal was to carry out an analysis of the energy efficiency of the renovation of the buildings in Juan XXIII neighbourhood previously mentioned. This implied to: Set a record of the initial energy demand and energy consumption before the retrofitting works, and then after the works have been concluded; Evaluate the proposed measures to improve the energy efficiency of the thermal envelope, in order to decrease the CO2 emissions. Compare the improvements of different strategies on energy savings and reduction of CO2 emissions, including those proposed in the initial project, in order to optimize and capitalize to a maximum level the resources to spend in similar future actions.

Reduction global percentages achieved in CO2 emission, demand and consumption (Begoña Serrano-Lanzarote et al, 2017)

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

What strategies to reduce energy poverty?

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6. REFERENCES

Begoña Serrano-Lanzarote, Laura Soto Francés, Leticia Ortega Madrigal and Alejandra García- Prieto Ruiz, Analysis of the Environmental Impact of the Energy Retrofitting Carried Out in a Low-income Residential Neighbourhood. The Case of Juan XXIII in Alicante, Spain, *The Open Construction and Building Technology Journal*, 2017, 11, (Suppl-1, M3) 65-82

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: SOLHUS1

CONTEXT: GARDSTEN, SWEDEN

ORIGINAL USE: MULTI-FAMILY HOUSING

USE: MULTI-FAMILY HOUSING

DESIGNER(S): nd

COMPLETION DATE: 2003

Keywords: User-oriented approaches, Occupant behaviours, Occupancy sensors, Climate-oriented design approaches, Climatic conditions, Prevailing Winds, Metering system, Living standards

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4. URBAN AND/OR BUILDING FEATURES

This project is located in Gårdsten, a suburban area 10 km to the north east of Gothenburg, which was originally built in the early 1970s (1969-1972). Almost from the beginning, lack of maintenance and local services, health problems, poor public transportation, unemployment, high rate of vandalism and crime and consequently social segregation and insecurity made Gårdsten a stigmatized problematic area in the city. All these, together with technical issues with the buildings and the unpleasant gray, brutal appearance of the environment had caused considerable vacant flats in the area (almost 30%). In 1996 Gårdsten was one of the most deteriorated living areas in Sweden when the city of Gothenburg decided to make a major change in this district.

The first action to regenerate the area was to make a physical refurbishment in order to provide the tenants with better living standards and the aim was to revitalize the social structure to create a more attractive living environment. The goals would not be fulfilled without active participation of the tenants in the process and an effort to integrate a community of which a large proportion was immigrants. Furthermore, to reduce the energy costs and use of renewable energy in order to make the development more sustainable, a renewable energy design was considered to be integrated to the renovation project.

Relation between main objectives of EE buildings, robustness criteria and HOMETEC factors

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

How to deal with the level of uncertainties?

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6. REFERENCES

VahidSabouri, , Two Case Studies in Energy Efficient Renovation of Multi-family Housing, *Master Thesis at Chalmers Architecture Design for Sustainable Development (MPDSD)*, Gothenburg, Sweden, 2012,

<http://publications.lib.chalmers.se/records/fulltext/158263.pdf>

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1. GENERAL INFORMATION

PROJECT: RETROFIT FOR FUTURE HOUSE

CONTEXT: BALHAM,LONDONUK

ORIGINAL USE:EDWARDIAN HOME

USE: HOUSE

DESIGNER(S): ND

COMPLETION DATE: 2011

Keywords:Monitoring Methodology, Differences between Forecast Consumption and Actual Use, Errors on The Initial Forecast Model, Energy and Actual Use, Energy Systems use On A Month To Month Basis, Legislation To Reduce Carbon Emissions

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The UK has enacted legislation to reduce carbon emissions by 80% from 1990 levels, by 2050 [Climate Change Act 2008]. Carbon emissions from the domestic sector account for around 25% of the total UK carbon emissions and of these, about 50% are due to space heating [DECC 2011]. With new construction making a tiny impact on these figures, improving existing housing becomes more important. This case study concerns the Haringey PassivTerrace, an extensive refurbishment of an existing mid-terrace Edwardian property aiming to save 80% of energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions. The house is a late Victorian/Edwardian terrace house typical of London, it now has 3 bedrooms with a bathroom and WC upstairs; downstairs there is a kitchen, living room and extra WC. The total floor area is 109m², with a total volume of 250m³. The Retrofit for the future competition aims to include the investigation of factors that could affect the rollout of major refurbishment programmes across the UK. During this project some issues have been discovered that affect the overall performance of the house and would be important to address in larger programmes. The Retrofit for the future competition aims to include the investigation of factors that could affect the rollout of major refurbishment programmes across the UK. During this project some issues have been discovered that affect the overall performance of the house and would be important to address in larger programmes.

5. FOCUS QUESTION AND MAP

What strategies to reduce carbon emissions?

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6. REFERENCES

Ben Croxford, Hawthorn Road PassivTerrace: Final Monitoring, Report for TSB, March 2013,
www.lowenergybuildings.org.uk/download.php%3Fid%3D70%26file%3DCroxford_2013_-_Hawthorn_PassivTerrace_Monitoring_Annual_Report_v7

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